

Graphical Abstract

Benzothiazole hybrid molecule with hydroxamic acid containing p-aminobenzoic acid

[4-(2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-ylthio) acetamido)-N-hydroxybenzamide]

New hybrid molecule of benzthiazole with hydroxamic acid recorded remarkable and potential anticancer activity against lung cancer cell line A549